

and average incidence of infected leaves were calculated for each field.

There is a significant regression function between disease incidence and severity ($R^2=0.954$). The results show that one can estimate leaf BI either by disease severity or by incidence on the top four leaves. Disease severity on leaf 3 is most representative of the average severity of all leaf positions (Table 1, 2).

Assessment of severity on a single leaf is more accurate than that on the whole plant because it is easier to do and saves a lot of time. The close relation between severity in leaf 3 and average severity of all leaves could be used for fungicide testing and crop loss assessment. □

Table 1. Regression models describing the relation between average BI severity and incidence at individual leaf positions. Bangkok, Thailand, 1987 dry season.

Independent variable	Dependent variable	Regression model	R^2
Average severity	Incidence on leaf 1	$y = 0.333 + 0.118x - 0.007x^2$	0.338
	Incidence on leaf 2	$y = 0.306 + 0.156x - 0.010x^2$	0.560
	Incidence on leaf 3	$y = x/(0.84 + 0.962x)$	0.857
	Incidence on leaf 4	$y = 0.272 + 0.193x - 0.012x^2$	0.657

Table 2. Regression models to predict average BI severity on all 4 leaf positions from an individual leaf position. Bangkok, Thailand, 1987 dry season.

Independent variable	Dependent variable	Regression model	R^2
Severity on leaf 1	Average severity	$y = 1.457 + 1.401x$	0.621
Severity on leaf 2		not significant	—
Severity on leaf 3		$y = 0.012 + 0.719x$	0.916
Severity on leaf 4		$y = 0.480 + 0.637x$	0.913

Orange leaf symptoms on rice

Y. P. Duan and H. Hibino, Plant Pathology Department, IRRRI

We tested eight rice varieties for reaction to orange leaf disease. Third- or 4th-instar nymphs of *Recilia dorsalis* free of the orange leaf agent were allowed to feed on source plants 2-3 d. Individual leafhoppers were used for serial daily inoculation feedings on 7- to 10-d-old seedlings in test tubes. Inoculated plants were grown in pots.

Symptoms appeared in IR36, IR50, and FK135 14-20 d after inoculation (DAI). The symptoms included the orange discoloration and inward leaf rolling typical of orange leaf. Infected plants died 35-48 DAI.

Reactions of 8 rice varieties to orange leaf. IRRRI, 1988.

Variety	Plants inoculated (no.)	Plants infected (%)	Symptoms ^a
FK135	38	29	Od, Lr,
IR36	38	26	Od, Lr, W1
IR50	40	48	Od, Lr
IR8	39	26	Od, Lr, R1
IR20	35	60	Od, Lr, R1
TN1	40	55	Od, Lr, R1
Reiho	37	38	Yd, Lr, W1
Fukumasari	35	43	Yd, Lr, W1

^a Od = orange discoloration, Lr = leaf rolling, Yd = yellow discoloration with rusty spots, R1 = ragged leaf, W1 = wide angle leaf.

Infected IR8, IR20, and TN1 plants developed deformed leaves with chlorotic and serrated edges and twisted leaf tips 8-12 DAI. These symptoms are similar to those observed in rice plants infected with ragged stunt virus. At 14-20 DAI, the tips of the second and third youngest leaves turned orange. Later, entire leaves became discolored and rolled inward; they eventually wilted. In TN1, about 90% of infected plants developed ragged leaves. Infected plants without ragged leaves died about 7 wk after inoculation, but those with ragged leaves died about 10 wk after.

Plants of japonica varieties Reiho and Fukumasari showed stunting, yellow discoloration, rusty spots on leaves, and wider leaf angle 15-24 DAI. The symptoms are similar to those caused by rice grassy stunt virus. Plants died 26-60 DAI.

IR20, IR50, and TN1 had higher infection than IR8, IR36, and FK135 (see table). None of the plants that showed symptoms after inoculation reacted with antisera to rice ragged stunt, rice grassy stunt, and rice tungro bacilliform and spherical viruses in the latex test or ELISA. □

Rice yield loss to sheath rot (ShR)

A. Surin, P. Arunyanart, R. Dhitikiattipong, W. Rojanahusdin, S. Disthaporn, and K. Soontrajarn, Rice Pathology Research Branch, Plant Pathology and Microbiology Division, Department of Agriculture, Bangkok, Bangkok 10900, Thailand

High-yielding rice variety RD23 is severely damaged by ShR (*Sarocladium oryzae* or *Acrocyndrium oryzae*) at heading. We measured yield loss caused by the disease and the effect of fungicides on its control Jun-Dec 1986.

RD23 was transplanted in 4- × 6-m² plots in an incomplete block design with 4 replications of treated-not treated plots

and 2 replications of disease-free plots. The treatment consisted of weekly application of carbendazim.

Linear regression between % ShR disease 1 wk before harvest and % yield loss at Pathum Thani Rice Research Center, Thailand, 1986 wet season.